

1 **PINCELO**

2 Today, Pincelo is a hub of tourist and wine-related activity, boasting a number of boat
3 tour operators, cultural attractions, accommodation providers, water sports facilities and
4 wineries.

5 **PORTOTIDE BRIDGE**

6 This bridge linked the villages of Portotide, on the banks of the O Saviñao, and Pincelo,
7 which belongs to Chantada. It was originally 35 metres long, but with the construction of
8 the Os Peares reservoir, it had to be rebuilt at a higher level and extended to 125 metres,
9 whilst retaining the original iron structure in its central section.

10 Furthermore, the reservoir caused the village of Portotide to be submerged and Pincelo to
11 lose much of its farmland, with the village now lying at the same level as the waters of
12 the River Miño.

13 **ESTHER TEIJEIRO**

14 Among all these wineries, Diego de Lemos stands out. Owned by Esther Teijeiro Lemos
15 (Nogueira de Miño, 1936), she was one of the first female winemakers to establish the
16 Ribeira Sacra Designation of Origin and a pioneer in producing organic wine as far back
17 as the year 2000.

18 Her intrepid nature and expertise have earned her numerous awards for her wines,
19 including recognition as a female entrepreneur and for environmental excellence, and she
20 has also featured in numerous reports, documentaries and television programmes.

21 Hers is a traditional winery, with the rear section carved out of the rock to maintain ideal
22 temperature and humidity conditions inside. She produces red wines from Mencía grapes
23 and white wines from Godello and Treixadura.

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